

Bisphenol A Contamination in Aquatic Environments: A Current Review of Remediation Technologies and Pathways for Future Solutions

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Abstract

Bisphenol A (BPA), an endocrine-disrupting chemical, has raised significant environmental and public health concerns due to its widespread use and persistence in aquatic environments. This review explores the contamination of aquatic environment by BPA, its sources, and its toxicological effects on ecosystems and human health. BPA, primarily used in the manufacturing of polycarbonate plastics and epoxy resins, enters water bodies through industrial effluents, landfill leachates, and wastewater discharge. Its harmful impact includes endocrine disruption, reproductive disorders, and developmental toxicity, which affects both aquatic life and humans who rely on contaminated water sources. Current remediation strategies, such as Advanced Oxidation Processes (AOPs), have shown promise in degrading BPA but face challenges in scalability and efficiency. Technologies such as ozonation, Fenton's process, and peracetic acid based systems have been explored, showing varying degrees of effectiveness in removing BPA from contaminated water. Additionally, the use of carbonaceous materials like activated carbon and biochar has enhanced the efficiency of these processes. Despite these advancements, complete BPA degradation remains difficult, and further research is required to optimize these technologies. Moreover, stronger regulatory frameworks are essential to manage BPA contamination, with varying regulations being implemented across different regions. The review concludes by highlighting the need for integrated approaches combining improved treatment technologies and stricter regulations to mitigate BPA contamination and safeguard environmental and public health.

Keywords: *Bisphenol A, environmental contamination, Advanced Oxidation Processes, degradation, regulation, aquatic ecosystems.*

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Introduction

Emerging pollutants (EPs), also known as contaminants of emerging concern (CECs), have become a major environmental and public health issue due to their increasing prevalence in water, soil, and air. Many of these substances remain unregulated, leading to uncontrolled contamination of natural resources such as surface water, groundwater, and wastewater (Mishra et al., 2023; Vargas-Berrones et al., 2020). Among these, bisphenol A (BPA) stands out as a particularly concerning pollutant due to its widespread use, environmental persistence, and harmful effects on both ecosystems and human health (Schmidlin et al., 2023).

BPA is a synthetic chemical primarily used in manufacturing polycarbonate plastics and epoxy resins, which are found in numerous consumer products, including food containers, medical devices, and thermal paper (Gibson et al., 2023). Its endocrine-disrupting properties allow it to interfere with hormonal systems, leading to reproductive disorders, developmental abnormalities, and increased risks of diseases such as cancer (Guo et al., 2025; Shankar & Teppala, 2012). Due to its extensive industrial and commercial use, BPA enters water bodies through wastewater discharge, landfill leachate, and industrial effluents (Kleywegt et al., 2011; Narevski et al., 2021). Once in the environment, it bioaccumulates in aquatic organisms, posing long-term risks to wildlife and humans who rely on contaminated water sources (T. L. Rocha et al., 2024).

The health impacts of BPA exposure are well-documented, with studies linking it to obesity, metabolic disorders, cardiovascular diseases, and reproductive issues (Huo et al., 2015; K. Y. Kim et al., 2019). Additionally, BPA acts as a teratogen, causing developmental toxicity in humans and wildlife (Shankar & Teppala, 2012). In aquatic ecosystems, it disrupts endocrine

functions, leading to reproductive impairments, developmental defects, and population declines (Bhandari et al., 2015; Langston, 2020)(Bhandari et al., 2015; Langston, 2020). Furthermore, BPA interacts with other pollutants, such as microplastics, amplifying their toxicity and ecological risks (Gao et al., 2023).

Given its global presence in water systems and its severe ecological and health consequences, effective strategies for BPA mitigation are urgently needed. While advanced oxidation processes (AOPs) and other emerging degradation technologies show promise, the development of cost-effective and scalable solutions remains a critical challenge. Additionally, stronger regulatory measures are essential to control BPA contamination and protect public health and aquatic ecosystems. This review examines the current state of BPA contamination, its environmental and health impacts, and potential remediation approaches, emphasizing the need for continued research and stricter regulatory frameworks to address this pressing issue.

Physicochemical properties of BPA

BPA is a synthetic organic compound, chemically known as 4,4'-(propane-2,2-diyl)diphenol, belonging to the group of bisphenols and diphenylmethane derivatives. It is an industrial chemical primarily used in the production of polycarbonate plastics and epoxy resins. The compound has been utilized since the 1950s and is produced in high volumes, exceeding eight billion pounds annually worldwide (AYAZGÖK & Tuylu Kucukkilinc, 2019; Zielńska et al., 2019).

The Water solubility CAS number and specific physicochemical properties of BPA are presented in Table 1. With a log Kow value of 3.32, BPA is primarily partitioned in the water phase, as its log Kow is ≤ 4 .

Table 1. Physicochemical Properties of BPA

Compound	Systematic name	CAS	Decomposition temperature	Water solubility	pKa	octanol-water partition coefficient (log Kow)	Molecular Formula
BPA	4,4'-(Propane-2,2-diyl)diphenol	080-05-7	>200 °C	<1 mg/mL at 21.5 °C	10.1	3.32	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ O ₂

Table 2. BPA Concentration Range in Water Bodies Across Different Regions and Sources of Contamination

Region	Water Body	BPA Concentration Range	Source of Contamination	References
Spain	River	129 ng/L	Industrial discharge, urban wastewater effluents, septic tanks	(Schmidlin et al., 2023)
China	62 DWTPs	4.7–512 ng/L	Plastic manufacturing, inadequate industrial wastewater treatment	(Fan et al., 2013)
South Africa	Drinking water	0.01-28.83 ng/L	Ineffective <u>water treatment</u> methodologies, source water contamination	(Van Zijl et al., 2017)
Brazil	Paraíba do Sul River	11.1–116.9 ng/L	Inadequate sewage infrastructure and untreated domestic wastewater	(Roledo et al., 2024)

The concentration of BPA is influenced by several factors, including local industrial activities, wastewater discharge, and the effectiveness of water treatment facilities. For example, areas with high levels of plastic manufacturing or poor sewage treatment systems tend to report elevated BPA concentrations in surface water and groundwater. In contrast, more stringent regulations and advanced treatment technologies often result in lower concentrations. Table 2 provides an overview of the BPA concentration ranges in different regions, along with the sources of contamination in each area.

Biological Degradation of BPA (BPA)

BPA is primarily degraded through microbial activity, with various bacterial strains playing significant roles. Strains from the genera *Pseudomonas* and *Sphingobium* have shown the ability to metabolize BPA into less harmful compounds. *Pseudomonas putida*, for instance, employs cytochrome P450 monooxygenase enzymes, which are responsible for oxidizing

BPA and facilitating its breakdown into smaller, less toxic molecules (Eltoukhy et al., 2022; Jia et al., 2020). This bacterium is particularly resilient to high concentrations of BPA, suggesting an adaptive mechanism that enhances its capacity to degrade this endocrine-disrupting chemical (Eltoukhy et al., 2020). In *Sphingobium* strains, such as *Sphingobium sp. YC-JY1*, hydroxylation and ring cleavage reactions allow for BPA degradation, leading to mineralization into carbon dioxide (Jia et al., 2020; Zhou et al., 2015). The involvement of cytochrome P450 monooxygenase in these processes underscores its critical role in BPA breakdown (Zhou et al., 2015). Microbial communities, rather than isolated species, have also been shown to facilitate BPA degradation through synergistic interactions. Intermediate by-products produced by one bacterium are utilized by others, contributing to the complete mineralization of BPA into harmless by-products such as carbon dioxide (Yu et al., 2019).

Environmental factors such as oxygen availability also influence the rate of BPA

degradation. Aerobic conditions support aerobic microbial communities, which degrade BPA more effectively. Under anaerobic conditions, microbial degradation of BPA is less efficient, although some anaerobic microbes can still facilitate the process (Im & Löffler, 2016). Nutrient availability and co-substrates are important for microbial growth and degradation efficiency. Studies by (Ferro Orozco et al., 2015) and (Eio et al., 2014) emphasize the role of these factors in optimizing microbial metabolism during BPA degradation. In wastewater treatment plants, the use of activated sludge systems has proven effective in reducing BPA levels. Although significant reductions are typically observed, complete removal remains challenging, with residual BPA often detected in treated effluent (Ahmed et al., 2017; Melcer & Klečka, 2011). Persistent BPA concentrations in treated wastewater highlight the need for further optimization of biological treatment processes (Zielińska et al., 2016).

Advance Oxidation Processes

Traditional water treatment methods, such as filtration, and chlorination, have proven ineffective in removing BPA from water due to its chemical stability and resistance to biodegradation (Abu Hasan et al., 2023). BPA's hydrophobic nature and persistence in the environment require more advanced and efficient treatment methods that can break down its complex chemical structure. These challenges have led to the increased adoption of AOPs, which generate highly reactive hydroxyl radicals ($\text{OH}\cdot$) capable of efficiently degrading BPA and other persistent pollutants (Giwa et al., 2021). There is variety of AOPs that can degrade BPA, which include methods such as ozonation, UV/ H_2O_2 , and peracetic acid-based AOPs, generate hydroxyl radicals that effectively break down a wide range of organic pollutants, including BPA, into less harmful byproducts (Pokkiladathu et al., 2022; Schmidlin et al., 2023; Sharma et al., 2015; Su et al., 2023).

Ozonation

Ozonation is another effective method for the chemical degradation of BPA due to its strong oxidative potential and the generation of

hydroxyl radicals ($\cdot\text{OH}$), which are crucial for breaking down organic pollutants. Ozone reacts with BPA, forming reactive intermediates that eventually lead to its degradation, with studies indicating that ozonation can achieve near-complete removal of BPA, particularly at lower concentrations (Ahmad et al., 2015; Han et al., 2022). However, at higher BPA concentrations, the efficiency of the process decreases due to the ozone demand reaching saturation (Lv et al., 2016). The hydroxyl radicals generated during ozonation play a significant role in accelerating the oxidation of BPA, contributing to the mineralization of by-products into less toxic substances (Ahmad et al., 2015). The efficiency of this process is also influenced by various factors, including ozone dosage, pH, and temperature, with higher ozone concentrations generally leading to better degradation results (Han et al., 2022). Nonetheless, ozonation often results in partial degradation rather than complete mineralization, necessitating further treatment steps to remove residual by-products (Ahmad et al., 2015). To improve efficiency and minimize the formation of toxic by-products, recent studies have suggested the use of heterogeneous catalysts and other oxidants in combination with ozonation (Han et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2020). The incorporation of Fe_3O_4 - MnO_2 magnetic composites as catalysts has also been found to enhance the degradation efficiency of BPA in aqueous systems, improving both the reaction rate and transformation pathways (Zhang et al., 2020). Despite the promise of ozonation, its application in large-scale water treatment systems requires optimization to ensure complete degradation and reduce operational challenges (Lv et al., 2016).

Fenton and Electro-Fenton

The Fenton process, which involves the reaction of hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) with ferrous ions (Fe^{2+}) to generate hydroxyl radicals ($\cdot\text{OH}$), has been widely studied for the degradation of BPA in aqueous solutions. The hydroxyl radicals generated in this process are highly reactive and break down the complex BPA molecules into simpler, less harmful byproducts. Research shows that the efficiency of BPA degradation via

Fenton's process is significantly influenced by several operational parameters, including pH, temperature, and the ratio of hydrogen peroxide to ferrous ions. Optimal degradation typically occurs at acidic pH values around 3, as this enhances the stability of the reactive radicals (Huang et al., 2013; Rivero et al., 2014). Studies have demonstrated near-complete removal of BPA under optimal conditions, with (Huang et al., 2013) reporting improved removal rates with initial H_2O_2 concentrations between 1-5 mM. However, at higher concentrations, H_2O_2 can scavenge hydroxyl radicals, reducing degradation efficiency (Huang et al., 2013). The Fenton process is known for its rapid kinetics, making it an effective method for quick BPA removal (Ioan et al., 2007).

On the other hand, the Electro-Fenton process enhances BPA degradation by continuously generating H_2O_2 through the electrochemical reduction of oxygen at the cathode. This provides a sustained supply of hydroxyl radicals, improving the overall effectiveness of the degradation process (Gözmen et al., 2003). Li et al (Li et al., 2020) found that the Electro-Fenton process could accumulate up to 70 mg/L of H_2O_2 after 180 minutes, contributing to sustained BPA removal. This continuous generation of reactive species allows the process to maintain optimal conditions for BPA degradation over longer periods, thus improving the efficiency compared to conventional Fenton reactions (Boye et al., 2002). The use of Fe-loaded biochar as a catalyst has been shown to further enhance both the activity and recyclability of the Electro-Fenton process, highlighting its potential for large-scale applications (He et al., 2014). In addition, studies have demonstrated that the Electro-Fenton method typically exhibits superior performance over conventional Fenton due to its ability to maintain consistent reaction conditions and reduce hydrogen peroxide consumption (Manivasagan et al., 2012). The Electro-Fenton process also reduces the production of harmful byproducts, making it a more controlled and environmentally friendly method for BPA treatment (Chmayssem et al., 2023; Chmayssem et al., 2017). Scaling up the Electro-Fenton process, particularly using fixed-bed reactors,

could further enhance its effectiveness in industrial applications for BPA removal (Chmayssem et al., 2023).

Peracetic acid (PAA)

PAA, due to its strong oxidizing properties, facilitates the breakdown of BPA through the generation of acetylperoxyl radicals, which actively decompose organic contaminants (J. Kim et al., 2019; Zhao et al., 2021). The efficiency of BPA degradation by PAA is influenced by several operational parameters such as concentration, reaction time, and pH, with acidic conditions enhancing the reactivity of PAA and thus improving its degradation potential (Yang et al., 2023). Specifically, optimal pH values below the pKa of PAA (8.2) promote the existence of PAA in its non-dissociated, more reactive form, thereby accelerating BPA removal (Yang et al., 2023). In addition, combining PAA with transition metals, particularly Fe(II), has shown a significant enhancement in BPA degradation rates. The Fe(II)/PAA system generates additional reactive radicals, increasing the overall efficiency of the oxidation process (J. Kim et al., 2019). PAA's ability to decompose organic pollutants results in less toxic byproducts, thereby addressing environmental concerns associated with residual toxicity (Costa et al., 2015). Reaction kinetics indicate that PAA can achieve high degradation rates in relatively short treatment times, with concentrations as low as 12% PAA resulting in significant BPA removal within one hour of treatment (Luongo et al., 2020). PAA also offers advantages over traditional oxidants like chlorine-based compounds, producing fewer harmful by-products and thus presenting a more environmentally friendly solution for BPA removal (Kim & Huang, 2020; Luongo et al., 2020).

Carbonaceous materials, such as graphene, carbon nanotubes, biochar, and activated carbon, play a significant role in AOPs for BPA degradation. These materials are valued for their high surface area, adsorption capacity, and ability to generate Reactive Oxygen Species (ROS), which enhance the efficiency of BPA removal. By facilitating oxidative reactions and supporting photocatalytic and electrochemical processes,

carbonaceous materials improve the overall performance of AOPs in degrading BPA and other contaminants. Table 1 summarizes the key

carbonaceous nanomaterials used in AOPs for BPA degradation.

Table 3. Summary of Carbonaceous Nanomaterials for BPA Removal in AOPs

Carbonaceous Nanomaterials	Key Properties	Role in AOPs	Reference
Graphene & Reduced Graphene Oxide (rGO)	High surface area, electrical conductivity, enhances electron transfer	Supports photocatalytic and electrochemical AOPs, facilitates ROS generation	(Gandhi et al., 2016; Perreault et al., 2015)
Carbon Nanotubes (CNTs)	High surface area, mechanical strength promote radical generation	Adsorbs BPA, enhances photocatalytic degradation, and promotes ROS generation	(Bhatia & Datta, 2019)
Biochar	Cost-effective, renewable, enhances microbial activity, and adsorbs BPA	Adsorbs BPA, enhances degradation efficiency in combination with AOPs	(Tang et al., 2022)
Activated Carbon	High adsorption capacity, facilitates oxidation, and improves AOP efficiency	Adsorbs BPA, catalyzes oxidants (ozone, hydrogen peroxide), and improves AOP efficiency	(Bautista-Toledo et al., 2005)

Global Regulatory Landscape for BPA Contamination

The Global Regulatory Landscape for BPA reveals significant variations in approaches across regions, influenced by scientific evidence, public health concerns, and economic factors. In North America, the United States has implemented a ban on BPA in baby bottles and sippy cups, and U.S. producer of thermal receipts removed BPA from its formulation (Usman & Ahmad, 2016). Canada took more aggressive action by becoming the first jurisdiction to ban BPA in baby bottles in 2010 and classifying it as a toxic substance under the Canadian Environmental Protection Act (CEPA) in 2014, leading to stricter controls (Ellis et al., 2021). In the European Union (EU), BPA has been banned in baby bottles since 2011 and is included in the Registration, Evaluation, Authorization, and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH) regulation, though debates continue about acceptable levels of BPA in food-contact materials (Neri et al., 2024). In Asia, Japan regulates BPA through voluntary industry measures and government guidance rather than legal bans (Gys et al., 2020). China regulates BPA through strict migration limits (0.05 mg/kg for infant products) under standards GB 9685-2016 and

GB 4806.6-2016, effectively restricting its use in food packaging and baby bottles without implementing a complete ban. The country maintains a risk-control approach, focusing on permissible exposure levels rather than outright prohibition of BPA. These standards functionally eliminate BPA from infant products by requiring non-detectable migration limits and promoting safer material alternatives. In South Africa, BPA was banned in polycarbonate infant feeding bottles in 2011, prohibiting their manufacture, import, export, and sale, as part of efforts to protect infants from BPA exposure (Ologundudu et al., 2025). Similarly, Brazil has made significant regulatory moves, with the Brazilian Health Regulatory Agency establishing in 2011 that the migration of BPA from plastic materials and similar articles should not exceed a specific migration limit of 0.6 mg/kg of food, aligning with the European Union's Commission Regulation (P. R. S. Rocha et al., 2024).

The figure 2 provides an overview of global regulations regarding BPA in food-contact materials, specifically focusing on the bans and restrictions implemented by various countries. The regulations reflect growing concerns about the safety of BPA, particularly in products for infants and children. Notably, the European Union and South Korea have established

stringent migration limits for BPA in food-contact materials, while Canada, Japan, and Brazil have banned BPA in polycarbonate baby bottles. Some countries, like the United States, have implemented voluntary phase-outs, with certain states imposing their own restrictions.

China has set specific migration limits for BPA, while South Africa officially prohibited the manufacture, importation, exportation, and sale of polycarbonate infant feeding bottles containing BPA under the Foodstuffs, Cosmetics and Disinfectants Act.

Figure 1. Global Timeline of BPA Regulatory Milestones in Consumer Products

Advancing Research to Combat BPA Contamination in Aquatic Environments

Growing concerns about BPA’s environmental and health impacts highlight the need for improved remediation technologies and deeper scientific understanding. Key research priorities include optimizing AOPs, developing efficient catalysts, and studying degradation byproducts to assess toxicity. Research should also examine BPA analogs (BPS, BPF), environmental behavior across ecosystems, and interactions with other pollutants like microplastics. Also, long-term exposure studies and community monitoring programs are important for assessing risks and informing policy decisions to protect aquatic ecosystems and public health.

Policy Recommendations

To mitigate BPA contamination, policymakers should implement comprehensive bans on BPA in all consumer products while incentivizing safer alternatives. Advanced Oxidation Processes (AOPs) should be integrated into wastewater treatment, supported by funding for research and pilot projects. Public-private partnerships can accelerate scalable solutions, and awareness campaigns should promote BPA-free products and proper disposal. National monitoring programs are needed to track contamination, and interagency collaboration will ensure cohesive strategies for protecting ecosystems and public health. Figure 2 illustrates a comprehensive strategy for mitigating BPA contamination through integrated policy actions.

Figure 2. Comprehensive Strategy for Mitigating BPA Contamination in Aquatic Environments

Conclusion

The growing concern over the widespread contamination of BPA in aquatic environments highlights the urgent need for effective remediation technologies and regulatory measures. BPA, due to its pervasive use in industrial products and its persistence in the environment, has been shown to pose significant ecological and human health risks, including endocrine disruption and developmental abnormalities. While traditional water treatment methods have proven inadequate for effectively removing emerging pollutants such as BPA, AOPs, including ozonation, photolysis, and Fenton-based methods, have emerged as promising solutions, offering improved degradation efficiency through the generation of highly reactive hydroxyl radicals. The integration of carbonaceous materials like activated carbon and biochar has shown potential to enhance these processes, offering cost-effective and efficient ways to remove BPA from contaminated water sources. Despite these advances, challenges remain, including high operational costs, energy consumption, and the formation of potentially harmful byproducts during degradation. Therefore, future research

should focus on optimizing AOPs, developing more efficient catalysts, and investigating the environmental fate of degradation byproducts. Moreover, a global regulatory framework is essential to standardize BPA limits in water bodies, promote stricter controls on its use, and ensure the protection of both public health and aquatic ecosystems. A comprehensive and integrated approach, combining advanced treatment technologies with robust regulatory measures, will be crucial to mitigate the risks posed by BPA and ensure sustainable environmental management.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

References

- Abu Hasan, H., Muhamad, M. H., Budi Kurniawan, S., Buhari, J., & Husain Abuzeyad, O. (2023). Managing Bisphenol A Contamination: Advances in Removal Technologies and Future Prospects. *Water*, 15(20), 3573. <https://www.mdpi.com/2073-4441/15/20/3573>
- Ahmad, N., Yuzir, M., Yong, E., Abdullah, N., & Salim, M. R. (2015). Removal of bisphenol A

(BPA) in surface water by ozone oxidation process. *Applied Mechanics and Materials*, 735, 210-214.

Ahmed, M. B., Zhou, J. L., Ngo, H. H., Guo, W., Thomaidis, N. S., & Xu, J. (2017). Progress in the biological and chemical treatment technologies for emerging contaminant removal from wastewater: a critical review. *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, 323, 274-298.

AYAZGÖK, B., & Tuylu Kucukkilinc, Z. (2019). Neurotoxic effects of bisphenol A on SH-SY5Y neuroblastoma cells via nitric oxide. *Marmara Pharmaceutical Journal*, 23(3).

Bautista-Toledo, I., Ferro-García, M., Rivera-Utrilla, J., Moreno-Castilla, C., & Vegas Fernández, F. (2005). Bisphenol A removal from water by activated carbon. Effects of carbon characteristics and solution chemistry. *Environmental science & technology*, 39(16), 6246-6250.

Bhandari, R. K., Deem, S. L., Holliday, D. K., Jandegian, C. M., Kassotis, C. D., Nagel, S. C., Tillitt, D. E., Vom Saal, F. S., & Rosenfeld, C. S. (2015). Effects of the environmental estrogenic contaminants bisphenol A and 17 α -ethinyl estradiol on sexual development and adult behaviors in aquatic wildlife species. *General and comparative endocrinology*, 214, 195-219.

Bhatia, D., & Datta, D. (2019). Removal of bisphenol-A using amine-modified magnetic multiwalled carbon nanotubes: batch and column studies. *Journal of Chemical & Engineering Data*, 64(6), 2877-2887.

Boye, B., Dieng, M. M., & Brillas, E. (2002). Degradation of herbicide 4-chlorophenoxyacetic acid by advanced electrochemical oxidation methods. *Environmental science & technology*, 36(13), 3030-3035.

Chmayssem, A., AlChoubassi, G., Taha, S., & Hauchard, D. (2023). Electro-Fenton process at semi-pilot scale. A study to scale up the reactor for industrial applications.

Chmayssem, A., Taha, S., & Hauchard, D. (2017). Scaled-up electrochemical reactor with a fixed bed three-dimensional cathode for electro-Fenton process: Application to the treatment of bisphenol A. *Electrochimica Acta*, 225, 435-442.

Costa, S. A. d. S., Paula, O. F. P. d., Silva, C. R. G. E., Leão, M. V. P., & Santos, S. S. F. D. (2015). Stability of antimicrobial activity of peracetic acid solutions used in the final disinfection process. *Brazilian oral research*, 29(1), 1-6.

Eio, E. J., Kawai, M., Tsuchiya, K., Yamamoto, S., & Toda, T. (2014). Biodegradation of bisphenol A by bacterial consortia. *International Biodeterioration & Biodegradation*, 96, 166-173.

Ellis, J., Papaluca, A., Hamtiaux, M., Hales, B. F., & Robaire, B. (2021). A Case Study of Canadian Regulation of BPA: Insight Into the Science. *Duke Env't L. & Pol'y F.*, 32, 295.

Eltoukhy, A., Jia, Y., Lamraoui, I., Abo-Kadoum, M., Atta, O. M., Nahurira, R., Wang, J., & Yan, Y. (2022). Transcriptome analysis and cytochrome P450 monooxygenase reveal the molecular mechanism of Bisphenol A degradation by *Pseudomonas putida* strain YC-AE1. *BMC microbiology*, 22(1), 294.

Eltoukhy, A., Jia, Y., Nahurira, R., Abo-Kadoum, M., Khokhar, I., Wang, J., & Yan, Y. (2020). Biodegradation of endocrine disruptor Bisphenol A by *Pseudomonas putida* strain YC-AE1 isolated from polluted soil, Guangdong, China. *BMC microbiology*, 20, 1-14.

Fan, Z., Hu, J., An, W., & Yang, M. (2013). Detection and Occurrence of Chlorinated Byproducts of Bisphenol A, Nonylphenol, and Estrogens in Drinking Water of China: Comparison to the Parent Compounds. *Environmental science & technology*, 47(19), 10841-10850. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es401504a>

Ferro Orozco, A. M., Contreras, E. M., & Zaritzky, N. E. (2015). Simultaneous biodegradation of bisphenol A and a biogenic substrate in semi-continuous activated sludge reactors. *Biodegradation*, 26, 183-195.

Gandhi, M. R., Vasudevan, S., Shibayama, A., & Yamada, M. (2016). Graphene and graphene-based composites: A rising star in water purification-a comprehensive overview. *ChemistrySelect*, 1(15), 4358-4385.

Gao, D., Junaid, M., Chen, X., Liao, H., Chen, G., & Wang, J. (2023). Interaction of micro(nano)plastics and bisphenols in the

environment: A recent perspective on adsorption mechanisms, influencing factors and ecotoxic impacts. *TrAC Trends in Analytical Chemistry*, 165, 117132. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trac.2023.117132>

Gibson, G., Cundy, A., Kafwamfwa, N., & Stewart, A. (2023). “Old” and “new” contaminants and their management: learning from the past, looking to the future. *Environmental Geochemistry and Health*, 45(4), 1091-1105.

Giwa, A., Yusuf, A., Balogun, H. A., Sambudi, N. S., Bilad, M. R., Adeyemi, I., Chakraborty, S., & Curcio, S. (2021). Recent advances in advanced oxidation processes for removal of contaminants from water: A comprehensive review. *Process Safety and Environmental Protection*, 146, 220-256. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psep.2020.08.015>

Gözmen, B., Oturan, M. A., Oturan, N., & Erbatur, O. (2003). Indirect electrochemical treatment of bisphenol A in water via electrochemically generated Fenton's reagent. *Environmental science & technology*, 37(16), 3716-3723.

Guo, Y., Li, B., Yan, Y., Zhang, N., Shao, S., Yang, L., Ouyang, L., Wu, P., Duan, H., & Zhou, K. (2025). Maternal exposure to bisphenol A induces congenital heart disease through mitochondrial dysfunction. *The FASEB Journal*, 39(2), e70351.

Gys, C., Ait Bamai, Y., Araki, A., Bastiaensen, M., Caballero-Casero, N., Kishi, R., & Covaci, A. (2020). Biomonitoring and temporal trends of bisphenols exposure in Japanese school children. *Environmental Research*, 191, 110172. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2020.110172>

Han, Q., Dong, W., Wang, H., Yu, B., Dong, Z., Li, M., Xie, L., & Dai, Z. (2022). Performance of ozonation on bisphenol a degradation: Efficiency, mechanism and toxicity control. *Frontiers in Environmental Science*, 10, 1009499.

He, Z., Gao, C., Qian, M., Shi, Y., Chen, J., & Song, S. (2014). Electro-Fenton process

catalyzed by Fe₃O₄ magnetic nanoparticles for degradation of CI Reactive Blue 19 in aqueous solution: operating conditions, influence, and mechanism. *Industrial & engineering chemistry research*, 53(9), 3435-3447.

Huang, W., Brigante, M., Wu, F., Mousty, C., Hanna, K., & Mailhot, G. (2013). Assessment of the Fe (III)–EDDS complex in Fenton-like processes: from the radical formation to the degradation of bisphenol A. *Environmental science & technology*, 47(4), 1952-1959.

Huo, X., Chen, D., He, Y., Zhu, W., Zhou, W., & Zhang, J. (2015). Bisphenol-A and Female Infertility: A Possible Role of Gene-Environment Interactions. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 12(9), 11101-11116. <https://www.mdpi.com/1660-4601/12/9/11101>

Im, J., & Löffler, F. E. (2016). Fate of bisphenol A in terrestrial and aquatic environments. *Environmental science & technology*, 50(16), 8403-8416.

Ioan, I., Wilson, S., Lundanes, E., & Neculai, A. (2007). Comparison of Fenton and sono-Fenton bisphenol A degradation. *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, 142(1-2), 559-563.

Jia, Y., Eltoukhy, A., Wang, J., Li, X., Hlaing, T. S., Aung, M. M., Nwe, M. T., Lamraoui, I., & Yan, Y. (2020). Biodegradation of bisphenol A by *Sphingobium* sp. YC-JY1 and the essential role of cytochrome P450 monooxygenase. *International journal of molecular sciences*, 21(10), 3588.

Kim, J., & Huang, C.-H. (2020). Reactivity of peracetic acid with organic compounds: a critical review. *Acs Es&T Water*, 1(1), 15-33.

Kim, J., Zhang, T., Liu, W., Du, P., Dobson, J. T., & Huang, C.-H. (2019). Advanced oxidation process with peracetic acid and Fe (II) for contaminant degradation. *Environmental science & technology*, 53(22), 13312-13322.

Kim, K. Y., Lee, E., & Kim, Y. (2019). The Association between Bisphenol A Exposure and Obesity in Children—A Systematic Review with Meta-Analysis. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 16(14),

2521. <https://www.mdpi.com/1660-4601/16/14/2521>

Kleywegt, S., Pileggi, V., Yang, P., Hao, C., Zhao, X., Rocks, C., Thach, S., Cheung, P., & Whitehead, B. (2011). Pharmaceuticals, hormones and bisphenol A in untreated source and finished drinking water in Ontario, Canada — Occurrence and treatment efficiency. *Science of the Total Environment*, 409(8), 1481-1488. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2011.01.010>

Langston, W. J. (2020). Endocrine disruption and altered sexual development in aquatic organisms: an invertebrate perspective. *Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom*, 100(4), 495-515. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0025315420000533>

Li, H.-C., Ji, X.-Y., Pan, X.-Q., Liu, C., & Liu, W.-J. (2020). Ionothermal carbonization of biomass to construct Fe, N-doped biochar with prominent activity and recyclability as cathodic catalysts in heterogeneous electro-Fenton. *ACS ES&T Engineering*, 1(1), 21-31.

Luongo, G., Previtera, L., Ladhari, A., Di Fabio, G., & Zarrelli, A. (2020). Peracetic acid vs. sodium hypochlorite: Degradation and transformation of drugs in wastewater. *Molecules*, 25(10), 2294.

Lv, X., Xiao, S., Zhang, G., Jiang, P., & Tang, F. (2016). Occurrence and removal of phenolic endocrine disrupting chemicals in the water treatment processes. *Scientific Reports*, 6(1), 22860.

Manivasagan, V., Basha, C. A., Kannadasan, T., & Saranya, K. (2012). Degradation of parachlorophenol by electro-Fenton and photo-Fenton process using batch recirculation reactor. *Portugaliae Electrochimica Acta*, 30(6), 385-393.

Melcer, H., & Klečka, G. (2011). Treatment of wastewaters containing bisphenol A: state of the science review. *Water Environment Research*, 83(7), 650-666.

Mishra, R. K., Mentha, S. S., Misra, Y., & Dwivedi, N. (2023). Emerging pollutants of severe environmental concern in water and wastewater: A comprehensive review on current developments and future research. *Water-Energy Nexus*, 6, 74-95.

Narevski, A. C., Novaković, M. I., Petrović, M. Z., Mihajlović, I. J., Maoduš, N. B., & Vujić, G. V. (2021). Occurrence of bisphenol A and microplastics in landfill leachate: lessons from South East Europe. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 28, 42196-42203.

Neri, I., Russo, G., & Grumetto, L. (2024). Bisphenol A and its analogues: from their occurrence in foodstuffs marketed in Europe to improved monitoring strategies—a review of published literature from 2018 to 2023. *Archives of Toxicology*, 98(8), 2441-2461. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00204-024-03793-4>

Ologundudu, O. T., Msagati, T. A. M., Popoola, O. E., & Edokpayi, J. N. (2025). Bisphenol A in Selected South African Water Sources: A Critical Review. *ACS omega*, 10(7), 6279-6293. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsomega.4c01686>

Perreault, F., De Faria, A. F., & Elimelech, M. (2015). Environmental applications of graphene-based nanomaterials. *Chemical Society Reviews*, 44(16), 5861-5896.

Pokkiladathu, H., Farissi, S., Sakkarai, A., & Muthuchamy, M. (2022). Degradation of bisphenol A: a contaminant of emerging concern, using catalytic ozonation by activated carbon impregnated nanocomposite-bimetallic catalyst. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 29(48), 72417-72430.

Rivero, M. J., Alonso, E., Dominguez, S., Ribao, P., Ibañez, R., Ortiz, I., & Irabien, A. (2014). Kinetic analysis and biodegradability of the Fenton mineralization of bisphenol A. *Journal of Chemical Technology & Biotechnology*, 89(8), 1228-1234.

Rocha, P. R. S., Moura, H. S. R. P., Silva, N. G., Neves, F. A. R., Sodre, F. F., & Amato, A. A. (2024). Exposure of elementary school-aged Brazilian children to bisphenol A: association with demographic, social, and behavioral factors, and a worldwide comparison. *Scientific Reports*, 14(1), 24355. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-67267-4>

Rocha, T. L., Felix, L. M., & Farias, D. (2024). Ecotoxicological Effects of Emerging Contaminants on Aquatic Species. In (Vol. 12, pp. 567): MDPI.

- Roledo, C., França, D. D., dos Santos Feitosa, I. R., Quinaglia, G. A., Montagner, C. C., Roubicek, D. A., & Dos Reis, A. G. (2024). A comprehensive study on bisphenol A and estrogenic activity in the Paraíba do Sul River, São Paulo, Brazil. *Journal of Water and Health*, 22(11), 2060-2075.
- Schmidlin, D., Scheiber, L., Teixidó, M., Vázquez, E., Criollo, R., Jurado, A., Puigserver, D., Burdons, S., & Enrich, M. (2023). Sources of contaminants of emerging concern in groundwater of Barcelona urban area. *Advances in Geosciences*, 59, 59-67.
- Shankar, A., & Teppala, S. (2012). Urinary bisphenol A and hypertension in a multiethnic sample of US adults. *Journal of environmental and public health*, 2012(1), 481641.
- Sharma, J., Mishra, I. M., & Kumar, V. (2015). Degradation and mineralization of Bisphenol A (BPA) in aqueous solution using advanced oxidation processes: UV/H₂O₂ and UV/S₂O₈²⁻ oxidation systems. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 156, 266-275. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2015.03.048>
- Su, Y., Yang, Y., Jiang, W., Han, J., & Guo, H. (2023). A novel strategy of peracetic acid activation by dielectric barrier discharge plasma for bisphenol a degradation: Feasibility, mechanism and active species dominant to degradation pathway. *Chemical Engineering Journal*, 476, 146469. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2023.146469>
- Tang, Y., Li, Y., Zhan, L., Wu, D., Zhang, S., Pang, R., & Xie, B. (2022). Removal of emerging contaminants (bisphenol A and antibiotics) from kitchen wastewater by alkali-modified biochar. *Science of the Total Environment*, 805, 150158.
- Usman, A., & Ahmad, M. (2016). From BPA to its analogues: Is it a safe journey? *Chemosphere*, 158, 131-142. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2016.05.070>
- Van Zijl, M. C., Aneck-Hahn, N. H., Swart, P., Hayward, S., Genthe, B., & De Jager, C. (2017). Estrogenic activity, chemical levels and health risk assessment of municipal distribution point water from Pretoria and Cape Town, South Africa. *Chemosphere*, 186, 305-313. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2017.07.130>
- Vargas-Berrones, K., Bernal-Jácome, L., de León-Martínez, L. D., & Flores-Ramírez, R. (2020). Emerging pollutants (EPs) in Latin América: A critical review of under-studied EPs, case of study-Nonylphenol. *Science of the Total Environment*, 726, 138493.
- Yang, S., Liang, Z.-H., Wen, Y., He, C.-S., Xiong, Z., Du, Y., Liu, Y., Zhang, H., Zhou, P., & Mu, Y. (2023). Gallic acid accelerates the oxidation ability of the peracetic acid/Fe (III) system for bisphenol A removal: fate of various radicals. *ACS ES&T Engineering*, 3(2), 271-282.
- Yu, K., Yi, S., Li, B., Guo, F., Peng, X., Wang, Z., Wu, Y., Alvarez-Cohen, L., & Zhang, T. (2019). An integrated meta-omics approach reveals substrates involved in synergistic interactions in a bisphenol A (BPA)-degrading microbial community. *Microbiome*, 7, 1-13.
- Zhang, H., He, Y., Lai, L., Yao, G., & Lai, B. (2020). Catalytic ozonation of Bisphenol A in aqueous solution by Fe₃O₄-MnO₂ magnetic composites: Performance, transformation pathways and mechanism. *Separation and Purification Technology*, 245, 116449.
- Zhao, Z., Li, X., Li, H., Qian, J., & Pan, B. (2021). New insights into the activation of peracetic acid by Co (II): role of Co (II)-peracetic acid complex as the dominant intermediate oxidant. *ACS ES&T Engineering*, 1(10), 1432-1440.
- Zhou, N. A., Kjeldal, H., Gough, H. L., & Nielsen, J. L. (2015). Identification of putative genes involved in bisphenol A degradation using differential protein abundance analysis of *Sphingobium* sp. BiD32. *Environmental science & technology*, 49(20), 12232-12241.
- Zielińska, M., Bulkowska, K., Cydzik-Kwiatkowska, A., Bernat, K., & Wojnowska-Baryła, I. (2016). Removal of bisphenol A (BPA) from biologically treated wastewater by microfiltration and nanofiltration. *International*

Journal of Environmental Science and Technology, 13, 2239-2248.

Zielińska, M., Wojnowska-Baryła, I., & Cydzik-Kwiatkowska, A. (2019). Sources and Properties of BPA. In M. Zielińska, I. Wojnowska-Baryła, & A. Cydzik-Kwiatkowska

(Eds.), *Bisphenol A Removal from Water and Wastewater* (pp. 3-28). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-92361-1_2